

DEEP IMPLEMENTATIONS OF METAPHORS IN ECONOMIC CONTEXT

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the various functions of metaphor in the economic context. The nominative naming function, informativeness function, mnemonic function and text generation functions are fully explained.

Key words: credit portfolio, military operations, visual representation, economic world

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola metaforaning iqtisodiy kontekstda tur xil vazifalari masalalariga bag`ishlanadi. Bunda nominativ atash funksiyasi, informativlik funksiyasi, mnemonic funksiyasi hamda matn hosil qilish funksiyalari to`liq yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: kredit portfeli, harbiy harakatlar, vizual tasvirlash, iqtisodiy olam

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена различным функциям метафоры в экономическом контексте. Подробно объяснены номинативная функция наименования, функция информативности, мнемоническая функция и функции формирования текста.

Ключевые слова: кредитный портфель, военные операции, визуальное представление, экономический мир.

When discussing globalization and economic problems, as well as solving situations related to the world economy, metaphor occupies a special place among language tools. In many literatures, it is noted that conceptual metaphor is one of the productive ways of reflecting concepts, objects and events related to the economy, games, sports competitions, and military operations allow visual representation of economic concepts. Thus, the metaphor in the economic text takes an active part in the complex processes of knowledge of reality and plays a major role in gaining new knowledge about the events taking place in the world.[2]

Metaphor, as a linguistic unit, carries a specific linguistic load in speech, and in order to determine the role of metaphor in language, we consider it appropriate to point out its main tasks. The following functions of metaphor are distinguished in scientific literature.[5]

1. Nominative function. One of the important functions of words used in a figurative sense is the nominative function (lat. nominatio - "to name,

designate"). This task is carried out using simple metaphors, such metaphors have lost their figurativeness and are considered metaphors that function directly as nouns: in English, Forgiven Sunday, black trade, pansies, fallen money, tax, money circulation, investment attractiveness, credit portfolio, economic growth, value chain, dollar falling, money exchange are examples of metaphors that have become a common unit. Thanks to the metaphor, concepts that are unclear or almost unclear in the nomenclature systems become specific. On the basis of the nominative function, an object or event of economic reality is given a metaphorical name and fills the stock of the economic vocabulary. As a result, new lexical units appear. It can be said that the nominative features of metaphors are evident in the process of translation, when words from the mother tongue are translated into other languages, and when images are created.

2. Informativeness (information) function. A complex but beautiful event is a metaphor that conveys information about a thing, object, event in a holistic, figurative manner, so the speaker must have a rich lexical reserve for its formation and creation. Through the communicative function of economic metaphors, economic processes are understood, information about events in the world of economy is expressed, it is possible to store and transfer them, and with the help of it, this information becomes audible and interesting to readers and listeners, for example: consumption mood of the population, free market relations, evokes familiar associations such as dealing cards.

For example in English:[1]

- A new commodity spawns a lucrative, fast-growing industry, prompting antitrust regulators to step in to restrain those who control its flow. A century ago, the resource in question was oil. Now similar concerns are being raised by the giants that deal in data, the oil of the digital era. (The Economist). The economic metaphor of the oil of the digital era in this sentence serves the purpose of providing information.

In Uzbek:

- In the currently developing market of the free economy, the consumer mood of the population remains an urgent topic. So, in both languages, the informative function of metaphors serves to convey information in the world of economics.

Mnemonic function. Mnemonics (from the Greek mnemonics - the art of remembering) is a system of methods that facilitate memorization and expand memory by creating artificial associations. Some mnemonists learn to use

various artificial methods in their acquisition, and they achieve the ability to quickly remember large amounts of even meaningless material. But the use of artificial methods to improve the efficiency of memory in a fundamental sense is secondary and auxiliary. In general, memorizing by understanding the meaning is a better and more effective method than memorizing mechanically. Metaphor helps to remember information better. The mnemonic function of the metaphor is combined with the functions of explanation in scientific and popular literature, genre-forming in folk riddles, proverbs, literary aphorisms, philosophical concepts, heuristic, i.e. thinking, creative thinking functions in philosophical scientific theories. When talking about an object/situation or action, along with a metaphor, some related folk wisdoms, proverbs, and the opinion of sages are remembered associatively: For example, Amir Temur understood the economy as the foundation of any kingdom. "Davlatu saltanat," says Temur in his "Tuzuklar", is alive with three things: property, treasure, and army. With this, Temur emphasizes that for the survival and social development of the state, first of all, it is necessary to have economic opportunities.

And in English:

"The body of society's life is economy, and its soul and spirit is spirituality," said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values".

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As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values (speech of the meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 19, 2021).

In the example given in English, the body of life is likened to the economy, and the word "The body of society's life is economy, and its soul and spirit is spirituality" spoken in a metaphorical manner is revealed in the next sentence. That is, the next line of the economic metaphor "The body of society's life is economy" mnemonically mentions that it is a strong economy based on market principles.

As can be seen from the examples, in both languages, these economic metaphors have a mnemonic function, and as a result, they help the information to be remembered better and more vividly.

4. Text generation function. Naturally, this function of the metaphor is related to the formation, expansion and interpretation of the text. For example, when it comes to methodology and method in science, it is defined as the doctrine of methods, methodology teaches how to approach methods and reality in general. This theoretical idea can be explained in a simple form by giving a metaphor, that is, the methodology is the road, and the method is the ability to go to the designated road on foot, by bicycle, or by bus (freedom of choice).

The lifeblood of the economy - the reforms implemented in the banking and financial system, which is the lifeblood of the economy, will inevitably serve to increase the economic potential of our country (Economic Bulletin of Uzbekistan: 2020.-№1.-B. 26).

In English we can find:

Know, the sun is tired:

It hides behind the mountains;

Ray repays behind a ray

And, scarlet, thin cloud,

Having pulled out his tired face,

Get out to rest.

It's time for him to rest.

In the quoted sentences, the metaphor serves to clarify and explain the content of the text. The words "The sun is tired, It hides behind the mountains, thin cloud" have become a metaphor. The exhaustion of the sun, hiding among the mountains is used here in a figurative sense. In both cases, the metaphor is used in the form of a sentence and serves to create a text.

Thus, all these metaphors play an important role in the discussion of economic phenomena, they attract our attention with the way of showing economic problems. All these metaphors have an important and special place among economic texts and are important in the emergence of economic problems, as well as in the resolution of conflicts and contradictions. In addition, the function of the metaphor in the economic text is to understand the state of the world economy, it allows visual, comprehensible and different description of economic concepts, and it provides definitions for complex phenomena that appear in nature.

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